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RESEARCHER MENTAL HEALTH OVERVIEW IN GERMANY

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What is in the news?

The following summary presents recent developments and news related to the academic sector in Germany, focusing on topics such as mental health, academic career progression, funding, and research culture.

Declarations of endorsement of Charter & Code: 52 organizations in Germany signed the Charter & Code for Researchers, including the German Rectors Conference (representing all universities) and non-university research organizations like Fraunhofer and Leibniz (both with more than 90 Institutes each) [1]. Update of the Charter & Code in the process [2].

The German law planning to reduce the time of employment between the doctorate and a permanent contract to three years [3] – essentially giving early career academics three years post-PhD to become full professors – has been taken back to the drawing board by the governing coalition. Current draft offers 4+2 years for the postdoc phase on position based on permanent funds whereas the “+2” is only possible with a tenure-track position [4].

[1] European commission, Declarations of endorsement of Charter & Code,

https://euraxess.ec.europa.eu/jobs/charter/declaration-endorsement#show_Germany

[2] European commission, EUROPEAN CHARTER FOR RESEARCHERS AND CODE OF CONDUCT FOR THEIR RECRUITMENT,

https://euraxess.ec.europa.eu/sites/default/files/revise_d_charter_and_code_hrs4r_info_day.pdf

[3] Ben Miller on X, <https://x.com/benwritesthings/status/1637762933873688580>

[4] Wissenschaftspolitik, Bitte freimachen

<https://www.jmwiarda.de/2023/03/19/bitte-freimachen/>

Funding for Research and Academia

The following overview provides an analysis of the funding landscape for research and academia in Germany in recent years.

In 2021 Germany invested 3,13% of GDP in Research and Development according to the German Federal Statistical Office [5].

Internal expenditure in research and development by sector, 2021: This pie chart visualizes the expenditure on R&D by sector in Germany in 2021. Light blue color visualizes business enterprise sector, dark blue color visualizes government sector, and pink color visualizes higher education sector [5].

[5] German Federal Statistical Office
https://www.destatis.de/EN/Themes/Society-Environment/Education-Research-Culture/Research-Development/_node.html

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Public sector funding

Research in Germany website [6] describes the research funding system in Germany. Germany is among the leading countries globally in government-backed research and development (R&D) investment. The public sector contributes approximately 30% of the country's total R&D spending, both in absolute terms and as a percentage of GDP.

Germany's governmental structure is built on federalism, fostering cooperation between the Federal Government and the 16 individual federal states (Länder). This collaborative approach leads to a nuanced distribution of responsibilities and financial commitments in the field of research and research funding, with both federal and state authorities making independent decisions.

Beyond supporting higher education, the public sector also funds non-university research organizations, which play a crucial role in nurturing research talent.

Funding bodies like the German Academic Exchange Service (DAAD) and the Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (DFG) receive continued support from both the Federal Government and the Länder. DAAD is the world's largest organization facilitating international student and researcher exchanges, while DFG focuses on selecting and financing top research projects in higher education and public research institutions in Germany.

[6] Research in Germany, <https://www.research-in-germany.org/en/research-landscape/why-germany/research-funding-system.html>

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Industry funding

In 2020, German businesses were the primary contributors to research and development funding in Germany. They invested approximately 71 billion euros in R&D, focusing on internal expenditure. These companies also establish and operate their research institutes in specialized domains and collaborate with public institutions through various channels. Moreover, German companies play a significant role in nurturing academic talent by providing funding for scholarships and supporting endowed professorships [7].

Funding by foundations

Germany boasts over 5,400 civil law foundations dedicated to advancing scientific endeavors. The Stifterverband, an association of foundations, made a significant impact in 2021, contributing 18.7 million euros to support education, science, and collaborations between the business and scientific communities. Furthermore, approximately 11.6 million euros were allocated for endowed chairs, further enhancing academic initiatives [7].

[7] Research in Germany, <https://www.research-in-germany.org/en/research-landscape/why-germany/research-funding-system.html>

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EU funding

It's worth noting that the European Union also plays a crucial role in funding cutting-edge research and exceptional scholars and scientists through Horizon Europe (2021–2027) [8], an ambitious research and innovation program with a budget of 95.5 billion euros. This program's "Excellent Science pillar" specifically backs pioneering research projects led by researchers themselves via the European Research Council (ERC) [9], provides fellowships and research exchanges through the Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions [10], and supports world-class research infrastructures.

Government funding

According to the Research in Germany website [11], government is the second greatest sponsor of research in Germany alongside industry.

[8] European Commission, Horizon Europe, https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/funding/funding-opportunities/funding-programmes-and-open-calls/horizon-europe_en

[9] European Commission, European Research Council, <https://erc.europa.eu/homepage>

[10] European Commission, Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions, <https://marie-sklodowska-curie-actions.ec.europa.eu/>

[11] Research in Germany, <https://www.research-in-germany.org/en/research-landscape/why-germany/research-funding-system/how-does-government-funding-work.html>

Persona of the Researcher on the Career Ladder

The following overview delves into the structure of the tertiary education system, the various types of higher education institutions, and the unique employment challenges faced by researchers, particularly those in temporary academic positions in Germany.

In numbers

The most comprehensive data regarding doctoral candidates in Germany are available through the National Academics Panel Study [12] that has run surveys since 2019. The population of doctoral candidates from the 2019/2020 cohort (data from the 2021 survey) with 14 381 participants has the following composition:

- 51% are or identify as female
- 21% have migrant background
- 11% are parents
- 50% come from a family where neither parent attended university
- 40% are part of a structured doctoral program
- 60% have two or more supervisors, 40% have only one supervisor
- 47% have an employment contract, 17% have a stipend, 36% receive no financial support

[12] National Academics Panel Study,
<http://www.nacaps.de>

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The survey also addresses aspects of satisfaction and well-being, though the latter is not currently available through the public portal. 13% of doctoral candidates indicate that they are dissatisfied or very dissatisfied with their supervision and 21% indicate that they are dissatisfied or very dissatisfied with support offers for doctoral candidates at their institutes.

There is increasingly a debate about the pay/income of doctoral researchers, who are commonly on 50 to 75% contracts whilst performing 100% and beyond in working hours. In some disciplines, like computing and informatics for instance, the standard contracts are 100% and this leads to large inequalities among PhD candidates and their incomes throughout Germany [13].

In general, PhD salaries are based on market conditions: in those fields where external career options are high, people with PhD get larger salaries. At the same time in those fields where external career options are low, people with PhD get lower positions and lower salaries.

In the area of stipend-funded PhD research funding varies significantly and often only provides for low incomes, especially if the stipends do not provide for health insurance or child/children allowances, which however most stipends nowadays do.

[13] VolkswagenStiftung,
<https://www.volkswagenstiftung.de/de/news/aktuelles/studie-zu-wissenschaftskulturen-wo-sind-impulse-noetig>

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It is to be expected that the proportion of doctoral candidates in structured programs will be lower in future cohorts, as the German Research Foundation (Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft, DFG) changed course in 2019 by focussing the funding of its excellence strategy on the excellence clusters and discontinuing funding for graduate schools that was initiated in 2006 [14]. Many graduate schools that were established at that time are having to find alternative funding streams if they cannot be incorporated into excellence clusters. Hence, it is to be expected that many graduate schools will be discontinued or have to reduce the portfolio of support offers available to doctoral candidates. The DFG does still offer its funding stream for new graduate colleges (Graduiertenkollegs) that can be funded for up to 9 years [15].

The Post-doctoral phase in Germany represents a very varied demographic, since this broadly is considered any academic who has obtained their doctorate but does not yet hold a professorship (commonly referred to as “Mittelbau” in German). For instance, junior research group leaders are widely considered to be post-docs, and intermediate career phases that are common in other countries, such as lecturers, are rather uncommon in Germany. Hence, this group is extremely diverse in its career stage, career progression opportunities, and other defining features. We refer to ‘What is in the news?’ in this report regarding the ongoing debate on the transition to permanent positions after a defined period of postdoctoral work.

[14] Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (DFG), Exzellenzstrategie des Bundes und der Länder, <https://www.dfg.de/foerderung/foerderinitiativen/exzellenzstrategie/>

[15] Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (DFG), Graduiertenkollegs, <https://www.dfg.de/de/foerderung/foerdermoeglichkeiten/programme/koordinierte-programme/graduiertenkollegs>

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In Germany, university professors are still predominantly male and of German nationality. Increasing the female proportion of professors has received a lot of focus in recent years, much more so than other features of diversity such as being of non-German descent. The 2021 study by the independent consultancy firm VDI/VDE, the [buwin-2021](#) study revealed that some progress has been made in the participation of women at professorial and leadership positions. In 2021, approximately 34% of professorial vacancies were filled by women, which is a significant increase from the 17% recorded in 1997 but obviously still short of parity [16]. The buwin-2021 study also revealed that 92% of academics in Germany under 45 years of age (professors being excluded) are employed on fixed-term contracts. Thus, permanent positions are essentially the reserve of professors.

[16] Bundesbericht Wissenschaftlicher Nachwuchs, <https://www.buwin.de/>

Persona of the Researcher on the Career Ladder

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Relevant references and resources

- [Long-term career tracking](#)
- [Enrollment as PhD candidate](#)
- [Max Planck PhD Net Survey](#)
- [BMBF Internalization strategy](#)
- [BMBF Excellence strategy](#)
- [BMBF Equality and diversity system](#)
- [DGF Basics framework](#)
- [VWFoundation Research Culture Report](#)

Academic System of the Country

This overview offers a concise analysis of Germany's academic system, emphasizing the structure and governance of higher education institutions, including public and foundation universities and research-oriented entities and the supportive role of key scientific and technological institutions. It also covers the demographics and distribution of doctoral programs, reflecting the country's focus on advanced education and research development in recent years.

Research in Germany website [17] says that Germany hosts approximately 420 higher education institutions, comprising:

- About 110 universities, including 20 technical universities.
- 210 universities of applied sciences, with around 40 being technical universities of applied sciences.
- Over 50 art and music colleges.
- 30 universities of applied administrative sciences.

The majority of students in Germany, approximately 90%, attend public institutions. Nevertheless, the private sector has been expanding, encompassing 150 privately funded universities, with nearly 40 of them being affiliated with churches.

In Germany, universities and equivalent higher education institutions primarily have the authority to grant doctoral degrees. Some federal states allow universities of applied sciences to offer their own doctoral programs in research-oriented faculties, though nearly 94% of doctoral students still pursue their PhD at a university. Increasingly, collaborative doctoral programs involve universities, non-university research institutions, or companies.

[17] Research in Germany,
<https://www.research-in-germany.org/en/research-landscape.html>

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Germany is globally renowned for its research and scientific capabilities, attracting scholars and students alike:

- Approximately 441,000 international students from various nations study at German universities and other higher education institutions.
- Over 5,700 foreign PhD students successfully complete their doctoral studies in Germany each year.
- Nearly 59,000 international academics contribute to Germany's higher education landscape.

Germany boasts a rich and diverse research landscape with:

- Over 1,000 publicly funded research institutions.
- Various research and development centers operated by industrial companies.
- The 18 Helmholtz Centers specialize in developing, constructing, and managing intricate research infrastructures. These include accelerator facilities, telescopes, research ships, and supercomputers accessible to Helmholtz users worldwide.
- The Leibniz Association serves as an umbrella organization for 97 research institutions addressing scientific challenges of societal and international significance.
- Over 85 Max Planck research institutes all over Germany and a few abroad under the umbrella of Max Planck Society.

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Image source: [Research in Germany](#) [18]

Among these institutions:

- Germany houses 44 federal research institutions dedicated to addressing research issues of political and governmental relevance. These institutions engage in fundamental research projects and provide up-to-date information in a service-oriented manner.
- Additionally, Germany's federal states operate research institutions that offer guidance to policymakers, conduct research projects, and manage activities mandated by law, such as approvals, testing, and regulatory framework development. Across Germany, there are almost 140 state-level institutions encompassing a wide array of research domains.

[18] Research in Germany, <https://www.research-in-germany.org/en/research-landscape/research-institutions.html>

Career Track for Researchers

The trajectory of a researcher's career in Germany is an intricate path that spans temporary and permanent academic roles, reflecting a multifaceted system that supports individuals from their doctoral studies to tenured professorships. This outline examines the general career progression, the stability and challenges of academic careers, and the support mechanisms in place for researchers at various stages.

The general career track for researchers in Germany starts with pursuing an own, original research project towards obtaining a doctoral degree. The doctoral research phase takes on average 4 to 4.5 years with a certain variability attributed to the prevailing research culture within a given field.

The results, i.e. the written thesis, have to be published either as a monograph or as a (compilation of) peer-reviewed paper(s) in scientific journals. In order to obtain the doctoral title, the thesis needs to be defended in front of a panel of experts. Interestingly, and different from most other national contexts, the tradition in German spoken countries calls for including the supervisor as the first examiner on the panel. Therefore, supervisors in Germany often carry multiple responsibilities with respect to their supervisees in that they function not only as supervisors, but also as thesis examiners and often even as their employers.

This setting may create multiple interdependencies that require sensible handling on both parts. On an international scale, the doctoral title works as a label for the ability to responsibly conduct independent research projects. It is the basis on which researchers are entitled to apply for their own independent research funding in Germany. In essence, obtaining a doctoral degree qualifies for ambitious career paths towards leadership roles in all sectors of society.

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The doctoral research phase is most commonly followed by postdoctoral research phase. This is the period of an early research career where decisions are taken towards either continuing on the intra-university academic career track or to transition to aspiring research or managerial positions in all sectors of society. While progressing on the academic career track researchers can advance to junior research group leaders, senior research group leaders, professors, or academic heads of departments or institutes. In industry, researchers can move up to higher levels of research, management or executive positions.

Continuous professional development throughout all (early) stages of career with respect to self-management and leadership skills, to scientific and science communication skills, to research ethics and integrity and broad digital literacy are essential for advancing research careers in Germany.

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German universities provide extensive support to doctoral (and mostly also early postdoctoral) researchers through a range of training programs and support infrastructures dedicated to improving the early research experience with the aim to develop their research skills, broaden their networks, and enhance their career prospects. These are most commonly:

- Graduate Schools offering structured disciplinary as well as interdisciplinary training and access to research networks
- (International) Research and Training Groups usually existing for a fixed term period and focusing on specific research areas and related training offers including opportunities to work in a research team and to participate in research projects
- Graduate Centers or Academies providing orientation, support and resources on a metadisciplinary level with an emphasis on fostering early research independence and providing career development support

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The sustainability (or lack thereof) of academic research careers varies at large depending on the chosen subject area and for the individual it depends on the transparent expectation management when embarking on a research journey.

For doctorate holders, the level of precarity can be high in the sense that they face intense competition for limited funding and a limited availability of positions at universities or research institutions. Fellowships can provide a temporary level of stability albeit mostly lacking access to social security benefits. Although mostly short-lived, fellowships do play an important role throughout career progression in the academic system given they document successful competitiveness of the awardee.

Fixed term contracts throughout advanced stages of the qualification phase and tenure track systems can provide some level of job security. They are highly competitive and therefore difficult to obtain.

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Academic research careers do require a dedication to continuously apply for grants, to regularly publish high-quality research, to attend conferences, and to network with colleagues. They depend on a high level of flexibility and mobility on a national and even international level.

While there are opportunities for stability in an academic research career, it requires dedication, hard work, and a willingness to adapt to changing circumstances. However, academic research careers share this level of challenge with any other ambitious, non-ordinary career in any sector of society aiming at leadership roles. It is fair to conclude that within early stages of academic research careers the employment is rather of temporary nature. Permanent positions are predominantly on offer for the more advanced stages of career maturation.

For example, postdoctoral researchers are typically employed on fixed-term contracts, with a limited chance of securing permanent positions. This holds true for university-based positions as much as for postdoctoral positions in research institutions and industry.

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German universities at large follow the EC's nomenclature and sub-summarize their doctoral and early postdoctoral researchers under the label ECR - early career researchers. The characteristics of ECRs are that they are still establishing their research profiles and may be seeking tenure-track positions or other career opportunities in academia or industry. The German academic system places a strong emphasis on supporting and nurturing the career prospective of young researchers. Several programs and initiatives provide resources, support and training for ECRs. Some examples include:

- The DAAD (Deutscher Akademischer Austauschdienst) is Germany's largest funding body with dominantly incoming but also outgoing (mainly doctoral) fellowships to undertake research projects across the globe [19].
- The DFG (Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft) provides numerous funding opportunities for ECRs, including postdoctoral fellowships and research grants [20].
- Participation in the EU-funded Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions. These programs provide funding for mainly postdoctoral researchers to undertake research projects in Germany or other European countries [21].
- The Max Planck Society offers funding for postdoctoral researchers, as well as training and mentoring programs to help ECRs develop their research skills and build their career profiles [22].
- The Alexander von Humboldt Foundation offers fellowships and grants to international researchers who wish to conduct research in Germany. It also provides support for ECRs through workshops and mentoring programs [23].

[19] Deutscher Akademischer Austauschdienst (DAAD), <https://www.daad.de/en/>

[20] Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (DFG), <https://www.dfg.de>

[21] Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions, <https://marie-sklodowska-curie-actions.ec.europa.eu/>

[22] Max Planck Society, <https://www.mpg.de/en>

[23] Alexander von Humboldt Foundation, <https://www.humboldt-foundation.de/en/>

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In Germany, following the doctorate and including a postdoctoral research phase, the next level of formal assessment before career advancement in academia is the habilitation. The habilitation phase is usually characterized by a fixed-term employment at a university and allows for securing grants, building one's own research group, performing teaching duties within the academic context and participating in academic administrative work.

The habilitation itself is a rigorous examination process that is primarily based on an individual's research accomplishments, teaching experience, and academic contributions. It typically requires publishing a certain number of peer-reviewed research papers or a (another) book. Other factors, such as grant income, are not typically considered in this process and tend to start playing a role when applying for a first professorship.

Notably, the traditional rules would usually require that the researcher leaves the university at which the habilitation was defended and receives an invitation for a professorship elsewhere. Exceptions are granted within the tenure track system on based on individual performance.

While in the humanities, the social sciences and in medicine, the habilitation is still the prevailing qualification step before a researcher may become a professor, the appointing of a researcher as professors may also be based on a "habilitation-equivalent" performance. This is becoming the more dominant path forward in the natural and life sciences as well as in engineering.

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Overall, the research career in Germany is highly structured. The country specific aspects that may distinguish the researcher career in Germany include:

- **Academic degrees:** The researcher career in Germany is based on a hierarchical system of academic degrees starting with Bachelor's, Master's, and Doctorate, being the highest academic degree. Roughly, 2% of the German population hold a doctoral degree. The professorship is not deemed an academic degree but a professional title. The postdoctoral phase(s) may serve individual qualification goals but do not come with a corresponding title or degree. The doctoral and professorial titles are highly respected in German society.
- **Tenure Track:** Germany's tenure-track system is similar to that in other countries, but its implementation varies from institution to institution. Tenure-track positions, with a clear path to tenure, have been introduced in recent years in German universities, in order to attract and retain top-tier researchers. These positions, however, are extremely limited.
- **Public vs. Private sector:** The majority of research funding in Germany comes from the public sector, with the government investing heavily in research and development. However, there are also many private research institutions, especially in areas such as technology and engineering. Researchers working in the private sector often but less frequently though than in previous decades have access to higher salaries than those working in academia.

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- **Research funding:** Research funding at German universities and research institutes is highly competitive, with grants often awarded on the basis of peer-reviewed scientific publications. German research institutions and universities attract significant funding from national and international funding agencies.
- **Mobility:** Researchers in Germany are expected to be mobile, often moving between institutions and countries to pursue research opportunities. This can be facilitated through exchange programs, collaborations, or job offers from other institutions.

Germany's strong commitment to high quality research and fostering research careers, combined with its robust public and private funding for research and development as well as its strong international research collaborations, have made it a highly attractive destination for researchers from around the world.

Mental Health and Well-being

This section explores the mental health and well-being in Germany, and briefly overviews the effect of the COVID pandemic on the public discussion about mental health.

In German society as whole, there has also been a marked acceptance of mental health as a topic that deserves a more open approach. Perhaps one of the most visible examples being the support of mental health programs and campaigns by the Deutsche Bahn Foundation that has included awareness-raising posters at train stations [24].

There have also been numerous German celebrities who spoke out about their mental illnesses, notably spearheaded by comedian Kurt Krömer who opened up about his depression in his television show Chez Krömer.

Undoubtedly, the COVID pandemic has had the unforeseen effect of positively impacting the way in which well-being and mental health concerns are more openly addressed in Germany.

[24] Deutschebahn, Förderung der psychischen Gesundheit
<https://fbir.deutschebahn.com/2021/de/stakeholder/gesellschaftliches-engagement/aktivitaeten-der-deutsche-bahn-stiftung/foerderung-der-psychischen-gesundheit/>

Mental Health and Well-being in Academia

This section explores the mental health and well-being among academics in Germany, and outlines several grass-roots and top-to-bottom initiatives addressing mental health issues in academia.

The topic of mental health in Germany, like in most countries, has long been seen and treated as a taboo topic. Within the context of the academic sector, the Nature-paper of Evans et al. [25] spurred a lot of discussions and prepared the floor for a German grass-roots endeavor organized and lead by the network of doctoral networks from the Max Planck society, the Leibniz Association, the Helmholtz Juniors and the IPP Mainz PhdNet [26].

The 2019 survey of the Max Plank Society PhdNet covered aspects of well-being and workplace culture in greater detail [27] and was preceded by their 2018 position paper on power abuse and conflict resolution [28].

Indeed, there have been a number of prominent cases of inappropriate behaviour by scientists in leadership positions reported in the German media, that also led the Max Planck Society to commission a survey of its working culture by the Fraunhofer institute in 2019 [29]. Hence, the debate around mental health and well-being in the academic sector is closely linked to the topics of power imbalances and precarity of working conditions in Germany.

[25] Evans, T., Bira, L., Gastelum, J. et al. Evidence for a mental health crisis in graduate education. Nat Biotechnol 36, 282–284 (2018). <https://doi.org/10.1038/nbt.4089>

[26] N2 - Network of Doctoral Researcher Networks,

<https://www.phdnet.mpg.de/n2>

[27] MAX PLANCK PHDnet, Survey Report 2019,

https://www.phdnet.mpg.de/145345/PhDnet_Survey_Report_2019.pdf

[28] MAX PLANCK PHDnet, Position Paper on Power Abuse and Conflict Resolution,

<https://www.phdnet.mpg.de/news/2018/power-abuse-statement>

[29] Fraunhofer IAO, WORK CULTURE AND WORK ATMOSPHERE AT THE MAX PLANCK SOCIETY,

<https://www.mpg.de/13631521/work-culture-atmosphere-max-planck-society.pdf>

Mental Health Support and Service Systems

This section explores the mental health and well-being among academics in Germany, and outlines several grass-roots and top-to-bottom initiatives addressing mental health issues in academia.

System of professional support

There are several types of professionals who provide mental health care in Germany, namely psychiatrists, therapists, and psychologists. Psychiatrists are medical doctors who specialize in the treatment of people with mental health diseases, and they can prescribe medication. A consultation with a psychiatrist can be prescribed by a family doctor. In some cases a family doctor can prescribe medication as well, or renew the prescription. This scheme is covered by both public and private health insurance. Note, that health insurance is mandatory for every resident of Germany.

A psychologist who is at the same time a psychotherapist in one of the three types of therapy mentioned can do services paid by public health insurance etc. Then there are "therapists" or "psychotherapists" in other fields, who do or do not have a degree in psychology, and thus are of varying levels of education and can provide the same services as psychological psychotherapists, but not as psychiatrists. If they want to offer their services through public health insurance, they usually need a degree as "Heilpraktiker", which then allows them to do certain things, but not medication, through public health. So, bottom line, the "hierarchy" in terms of what their training is and what they may do is psychiatrist - psychological psychotherapists (needs scientific study in psychology plus therapy training) - other therapist (usually without scientific study in psychology, some therapy training).

Mental Health Support and Service Systems

This section explores the mental health and well-being among academics in Germany, and outlines several grass-roots and top-to-bottom initiatives addressing mental health issues in academia.

Barriers to accessing the support

The main barrier to providing professional mental health care/treatment are the shortage of professionals and sometimes extremely long waiting lists (6 to 18 months) except for emergency cases.

It is rather challenging to get an appointment with a specialist whose services are covered by the public health insurance system. There is a shortage of professionals speaking any additional language to German in Germany, leading to bi-lingual (or multi-lingual) specialists being overbooked. However, the walk-in emergency mental health care for acute issues is available at hospitals in emergency rooms independent of the patient's capacity to speak German.

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Research institutes and universities usually have ties with local support systems (burnout clinics, on-site psychologists accepting walk-in appointments, etc.). Owing to the federal structure of German governance, there can be significant local differences in the way institutes of higher education and their support measures are organized as higher education legislation is administered on the state-level.

Typically, students have access to student counseling that are offered by the state-run organizations called “Studierendenwerke” rather than by universities. Studierendenwerke also manage university mensas, student halls/accomodations and provide advisory services on various topics. Psychosocial counseling is usually part of the portfolio of the Studierendenwerke. In most cases, PhD researchers are eligible to register with their Studierendenwerk the same as BSc and MSc students can, but not all of them do. This means that some doctoral candidates may not have access to mental health or other support provisions within their host institutes.

Large societies like Max Planck Society sometimes outsource mental health counseling services to third parties, providing anonymous support. Other research institutes have followed this practice and arranged similar external programs for their employees and students. These third parties are typically accessible over the phone 24/7, and can provide help and give referrals to other types of support/treatment.

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Peer-to-peer training options

An option to train local mental health peer supporters is available through Mental Health First Aider training at an accredited institute in Germany, that provides certified training in English and in German [30].

Since 2020, MHFA support has expanded significantly throughout the German academic sector, primarily through the advocacy of this model through the German University Association UniWiND. UniWiND also offers the MHFA training to its members [31].

[30] Mental Health First Aider training,
<https://www.mhfa-ersthelfer.de>

[31] German University Association UniWiND,
<https://www.uniwind.org/aktivitaeten/mental-health-in-der-promotionsphase-unterstuetzungsangebote-von-graduierteneinrichtungen>

Policy view on mental health and well-being

The mental health policy landscape in Germany is marked by several challenges and developments, yet the issue is recognized and addressed by the government.

In recent years, there have been significant developments indicating that mental health is becoming a prioritized subject in the German political landscape.

For instance, the Federal Ministry of Education and Research has invested in a National Centre for Mental Health Research [32]. In addition, the federal ministries of labour and social affairs (BMAS), Family Affairs, Senior Citizens, Women and Youth (BMFSFJ) and health (BMG) have launched an initiative to improve access to mental health prevention and treatment measures [33].

On October 9th 2023, Dr. Manuela Richter-Werling was awarded the Bundesverdienstkreuz, the highest civil decoration that Germany awards, for her founding of the charity "Irrsinnig Menschlich" (translated: Madly Human) that provides prevention programs targeted primarily at young people in schools, formative and higher education [34].

[32] DZP - Entwicklung eines wissenschaftlichen Konzeptes für das Deutsche Zentrum für Psychische Gesundheit, <https://www.gesundheitsforschung-bmbf.de/de/dzp-entwicklung-eines-wissenschaftlichen-konzeptes-fur-das-deutsche-zentrum-fur-psychische-14182.php>
[33] Bundesministerium für Arbeit und Soziales, Initiative Neue Qualität der Arbeit, <https://www.inqa.de/DE/wissen/gesundheits/offensive-psychische-gesundheit/opg-dialogforum/uebersicht.html>
[34] Irrsinnig Menschlich, <https://www.irrsinnig-menschlich.de/>

Stakeholders and policies

This section lists several yet not all stakeholders working in Germany on improving academic mental health.

The major organizations involved in the recognition and improvement of the status of researchers or subset of researchers

- N2: PhD network of Max Planck, Helmholtz & Leibnitz societies
 - ReMO
 - EURAXESS
- and others

Organizations or initiatives in the country that are advocating for the mental health and well-being of researchers

- Planck Academy
- PostdocNet of Max Planck Society (Mental Health working group)
- Local initiatives at Universities and Research institutes (Rostock university, Cologne University, Heidelberg University, and others)
- Graduate schools (Berlin School of Integrative Oncology, Dresden IMPRS graduate school, and others)
- Grass-root societies and initiatives (Jungchemikerforum, Scholar Minds, Max Planck Mental Health Initiative (formerly: Collective), Mental Health Awareness Week (MHAW), and others)

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Mental Health awareness week

- Typically all MHAW events are organized locally (at the level of an institution or a campus) by the bottom-up initiatives. The organizers may invite speakers, most of whom deliver talks for free as such initiatives don't have sufficient budget.
- The most global MHAW action is the one organized by the Mental Health Initiative (former: Collective). For several years MHI organizes MHAW with the support of PostDocNet and PhDNet of Max Planck Society, Dragonfly Mental Health and individual Max Planck Institutes. The events take place in October each year, held online and are open for all. The amount of attendees is around 2500 people. In 2023 MHI holds a set of talks given throughout the whole year as a pilot for a new format, as there were several complaints from people that attending many talks in one week is challenging.

The main barrier is the lack of centralizer and/or top-to-bottom funding of such initiatives, as the general funding system is very rigid (no spare money to pay speakers and organize events), a lack of awareness among heads of institutes therefore no willingness to overcome the lack of funding, as well as there are no paid positions for people who would be willing and capable of bringing the change.